

Achieving technological sovereignty of the Russian economy and strategic planning priorities

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Аннотация. В условиях ужесточения санкционного давления проблема инновационного развития и экономического роста российской экономики представляется актуальной. Для ее решения целесообразно использовать инструментарий стратегического планирования. В статье обобщены методы формирования и реализации стратегических программ в рамках государственной политики научно-технологического развития. Проведен анализ перспектив структурной трансформации и обоснованы приоритеты применения инструментария стратегического планирования для достижения технологического суверенитета российской экономики. Результаты исследования могут использоваться для прогнозирования инновационного развития экономики России.

Abstract. In the context of increasing sanctions pressure, the problem of innovative development and economic growth in the Russian economy appears urgent. To address this, it is advisable to use strategic planning tools. This article summarizes the methods for developing and implementing strategic programs within the framework of state policy for scientific and technological development. It analyzes the prospects for structural transformation and substantiates the priorities for applying strategic planning tools to achieve technological sovereignty in the Russian economy. The results of this study can be used to forecast the innovative development of the Russian economy.

Ключевые слова: *инструментарий, стратегическое планирование, технологический суверенитет, инновационное развитие.*

Keywords: *instrumentation, strategic planning, technological sovereignty, innovative development.*

Introduction

Today, Russia is implementing a new strategy for technological modernization and digital transformation of its economy. However, the worsening geopolitical situation in the world and global economic instability are causing contradictions between its constituent entities, negatively impacting the implementation of all these reforms. To achieve economic leadership on the global stage, the most important priorities for the Russian economy must be increasing technological competition and modernizing its structure. Clearly, to maintain competitiveness and ensure the progressive development of our country's economy, it is necessary to accurately predict structural shifts and implement policies aimed at achieving technological sovereignty [1].

To achieve these goals, it seems appropriate to use strategic planning tools. The implementation of the GOELRO plan is an example of successful strategic planning at the state level. Using strategic planning methods, Soviet Russia quickly solved the

most complex socio-economic development problems (housing construction, food supply, virgin land development, space flights, etc.) [2].

Modern realities dictate that the economy of any country operates within several technological paradigms (TP). In economics, this concept is used to describe the structure and organization of technological production processes that facilitate its progressive development. Each TP is characterized by its own production methods, technologies, and sociocultural characteristics. This multi-structured nature significantly influences the development of relations between economic entities and necessitates the development of new economic development strategies. For the strategic planning system (SPS) to function successfully, it is necessary to coordinate all economic regulation functions at the state level based on the priorities and goals of strategic planning. It is clear that without coordination of regulatory functions at the state level, the SPS will not be able to function effectively [2].

Literature review

The key thesis that increasing the rate of economic growth should be based on changing technical conditions and introducing innovative technologies into industrial production is reflected in the theories of economic growth by W. Rostow [3], industrial society by R. Aron [4] and J. Galbraith [5], post-industrial society by D. Bell [6], the industrial revolution ([7], [8], [9]) and advanced development [10]. It is confirmed by the industrial policy of reindustrialization (return) of enterprises to their territory, which is being carried out in the USA today.

Russian economists used the TU model as an analytical tool for analyzing technological revolutions [11, 12]. They defined TU as a "large complex of technologically linked industries" that, over a long period of time, was replaced by another complex promoting more innovative technologies. At the suggestion of Russian scientists, TU was defined as a set of industries "technologically linked to one another and forming reproducible entities" [13]. We will use this definition in this article.

While studying the problems of strategic state planning, Professor G.B. Kleiner noted back in 2011 that the planning period should be determined by external conditions, and not by the SPS itself [14]. Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences A.G. Aganbegyan believed that the lack of objective indicators of the beginning of a change in the technological paradigm is a limitation for the application of SPS tools for the purpose of transforming the industrial structure [15]. According to the author of the work [16], the development of the TU, as an essential component of the evolution of economic systems, introduces profound transformations into the SPS. Indeed, the key transformations in the SPS during the transition from the fourth to the fifth TU were associated with the following opportunities:

- Open access to large data sets has increased the informativeness of the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) on market development trends and supply and demand dynamics;
- The need to promote products on global markets has necessitated ensuring their global competitiveness using SPS tools;
- Ensuring competitive advantages through the implementation of innovative strategic planning methods;
- Increased competition has led to the introduction of SPS that are flexible and adaptive to constantly changing environmental conditions;

- Countries have increasingly begun to utilize strategic partnerships and network structures to improve the efficiency of production and innovation processes.

For comparison, let's consider the main changes in strategic planning priorities during the transition from the fifth to the sixth TU:

- reduced development timelines for strategic plans and programs at various levels;
- the development of artificial intelligence technologies, big data, and digital platforms required a revision of existing SPS business models and the introduction of digital tools for their development;
- increased uncertainty in the external and internal environments necessitated the use of iterative methods and scenario analysis in SPS.

Clearly, with the sixth TU in place, the priorities for applying the SPS must be refocused on exploiting new opportunities to improve the effectiveness of plans and programs. However, the main challenge for the modern Russian economy is the coexistence of both innovative industries and those of previous TU. State support for the latter is holding back Russian economic growth and causing it to lag behind developed countries in high-tech production volumes.

Materials and methods

In today's world, economic development in many countries is based on national SPS. However, some groups of countries have distinctive approaches to the practical implementation of functions such as prioritization, forecasting, indicative planning, budgeting, and others. Below, we briefly review three of the most well-known strategic planning models, which are used in various modifications in different countries.

The first model prioritizes budget planning and government regulation of economic development. It is used in the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom. The second model is characterized by the definition of strategic economic development goals at the government level. The implementation and coordination of long-term plans is supported by the budget. The economies of China, India, Japan, South Korea, and several Latin American countries are developing based on this model. The third model incorporates market regulation mechanisms. It calls for the periodic selection of socioeconomic development priorities, the formation of indicative plans, and the definition of benchmarks. This model is used by the economies of Vietnam, Cuba, and other developing countries.

Germany and China are leading the structural transformation of industry based on strategic plans

and programs for the economic transition to a new technological paradigm. Germany has been implementing the "Industry 4.0" program for over 10 years [17], while China has a strategic plan for socio-economic development, "Made in China 2025" [18]. This plan envisions China becoming the world's leading industrial power by 2049.

The gradual exhaustion of potential for productivity growth has prompted a number of leading countries (the United States, Germany, China,

South Korea, and others) to develop policies for accelerated scientific and technological development based on the introduction of breakthrough innovative technologies. To implement this policy, a number of strategies, plans, and programs have been developed at the state level to stimulate the emergence of innovative systems, the growth of scientific and technological potential, and the renewal of the industrial technological base (see Table 1[19]).

Table 1

Strategic initiatives for innovative development

Country	Document title	Period
USA	Modern American Industrial Strategy	Since 2020
	CHIPS and Science Act	Since 2022
Germany	Industry 4.0	2011-2020
	Expanded strategy for the development of high technologies	In development
France	Innovations – 2030	2013-2030
Italy	Industry 2015	2015-2025
Japan	Comprehensive Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation	2013-2030
EU	Open strategic autonomy	Since 2021
	Important Projects of Common European Interest (IPCEIs)	Since 2019
	Action Plan for Synergies between the Civil, Defense and Space Industries	Since 2021
	Roadmap for Critical Technologies for Security and Defense	Since 2022
	EU-US Trade and Technology Programme	Since 2021
	European Horizons and Digital Europe programmes	Since 2022
China	Made in China 2025 program	Since 2015
	14th Five-Year Plan	2021-2025
	Dual circulation strategy	Since 2021
	China's Belt and Road Initiative	Since 2016
	China Standards 2035	Since 2018
India	A Decade of Innovation	2010-2020

In Russia, the SPS is clearly structured and normatively enshrined [20]. It is based on forecasts of socio-economic development (up to 2036), scientific and technological development (up to 2030), and strategic development (up to 2035). The planning and forecasting period is defined as six years or more. Long-term plans are developed "every six years for 12 years or more." Strategic planning is tied to budget formation periods (three years) and six-year cycles of political system transformation. Priorities for the development of technology and innovation are defined in the Strategy for Scientific and Technological Development of the Russian Federation [21]:

1. Stimulating research aimed at developing innovative technologies.
2. Creating an interactive environment for intelligent, digital production. Developing green energy.
3. Optimizing the resource balance in the face of limited natural resources.
4. Ensuring the country's food security.

5. Adapting scientific and technological development to demographic and socio-technological risks associated with the increasingly complex living conditions of society.

The national program "Digital Economy of the Russian Federation" [22] defines the goals of modernizing production based on new digital technologies. These include the formation of a legal framework, the creation and development of new enterprises, and the development of infrastructure.

Results and discussion

The formation of public policy in the area of scientific and technological development is implemented through SPS. Direct and indirect methods are used for this purpose. These are presented in a systematic form in Table 2 ([23], [24], [25]). Using these methods and taking into account the new connections and dependencies of scientific and technological development characteristic of more modern TS, the strategic planning process can be improved.

Methods for implementing the strategic planning mechanism

Direct methods	Indirect methods
R&D funding from federal and regional budgets	Tax credits and incentives
Control over the procurement of technologies and innovations	Stimulating enterprises
Risk insurance	Accelerated depreciation
Subsidies for scientific and technical developments	Formation of innovative scientific and technological centers
Subsidized financing of individual innovative projects	Improving legislation in patent law matters
Providing government guarantees to attract investor funds to projects	Creation of a legal mechanism for large businesses to enter into the capital of small innovative companies
Institute of Special Investment Contracts	

In the context of the transition to the new TU, strategic planning for scientific and technological development should utilize a new economic growth model, technological leadership scenarios, and new approaches to managing scientific and technological change within the framework of implementing technological development strategies [26], [27]. These strategies could be structurally based on "institutes of professional customers" for innovative technological solutions (IPC ITS). They will assist industrial enterprises in the transition to technologies of the sixth TU through the development of regional technology platforms. These platforms will facilitate the implementation of the functions of "professional customers" and ensure interaction between all participants in the "science-education-production" system.

The foundation of modern strategic planning methodology is a system of long-, medium-, and short-term plans and programs. For each planning period, economic development priorities are selected and justified. This system should ideally include long-term concepts, medium-term programs, and indicative strategic development plans for economic activity (industrial production, trade, services) and social spheres (housing, health, nutrition, medicine, social services, etc.). The responsibility of all SPS participants for achieving the objectives set forth in development plans and programs should be legally established.

To improve the effectiveness of the IPC, targets should be defined for its areas of activity and accountability mechanisms for their timely achievement should be developed. These targets should be aimed at creating globally competitive manufacturing facilities. The key objective of this concept is to reduce the Russian economy's dependence on the economies of unfriendly countries. It largely overlaps with the import substitution policy implemented at all levels of government. However, its fundamental difference lies in its focus on progress in innovative developments, the creation of domestically produced products that

surpass renowned global brands in quality, and the accelerated digitalization of all areas of society.

It is easy to see that these processes require a long timeframe for implementation. The need to ensure technological sovereignty is recognized as an important factor in Russia's economic security. This is reflected in the Concept of Technological Development through 2030 [28]. Undoubtedly, this document is long-term in nature and strategically significant. Therefore, achieving technological sovereignty must be aligned with existing development strategies and the development of new programs.

Globally, there are numerous examples of how clearly defining strategic technological development goals at the state level enables the development of strategic programs and projects. To achieve these goals, it is necessary to focus intellectual, financial, and other resources on developing breakthrough technologies, which will lead to increased competitiveness for the entire economy. Certain potential for ensuring and strengthening technological sovereignty has already been accumulated.

In operational and functional terms, the policy for achieving technological sovereignty is based on the following principles:

1. Identifying technological areas whose import substitution is critical for the Russian economy.
2. Identifying priority areas for R&D.
3. Developing criteria for monitoring scientific and technological development.
4. Defining key indicators of scientific and technological development.
5. Identifying holders of scientific and technological competencies.
6. Identifying producers of innovative products.

In terms of information, the policy for achieving technological sovereignty is based on the implementation of the following provisions:

1. Identifying a range of critically important innovative products based on economic development areas.

2. Identifying economic entities based on economic development areas in the Russian domestic market and assessing the level of patent protection for the innovative technologies they use.

3. Identifying key indicators in areas of economic development that are critical for reducing import dependence based on the development of roadmaps.

4. Identifying technology leaders among economic entities based on economic development areas.

5. Developing a map of technological competencies and identifying their bearers.

In terms of information support, the policy for achieving technological sovereignty is based on the following principles:

1. Developing criteria for selecting economic development areas that are critical for scientific and technological advancement.

2. Ranking products and technologies whose import substitution is critical for the selected areas of economic development.

3. Defining priority R&D topics.

4. Defining priority areas of economic development for the creation of import substitution technologies.

5. Creating competency maps to identify economic entities as domestic centers of technological leadership in specific areas of economic development.

In the face of growing sanctions pressure, our country must quickly address two strategic objectives:

1) quickly bridge existing gaps in technological chains and replace foreign technologies in critical areas of development;

2) build scientific foundations for the highly competitive positioning of domestic products in international markets.

The authors believe that a policy for achieving technological sovereignty can be implemented using well-tested strategic planning tools. To mitigate risks in critical areas of economic development for our country, a number of strategic initiatives will be implemented in the near future, namely:

1) establishing alternative supply chains and increasing the efficient operation of air, rail, river, and sea transport, with a focus on developing a system of unmanned logistics corridors;

2) providing the automotive industry, transport, and special-purpose machinery manufacturing companies with Russian-made components;

3) implementing investment projects and conducting R&D in key areas of economic development;

4) ensuring energy independence through: expanding the range of domestically produced equipment, spare parts, and components; developing ING production and the necessary equipment; increasing the production of high-power turbines by domestic manufacturers; routine maintenance of existing energy facilities; accelerating the reengineering of components;

5) developing standards for components and tools and localizing their production.

Clearly, to address these challenges and implement key strategic initiatives to achieve technological sovereignty, the entire SPS should be transformed into a flexible toolkit that enables Russian manufacturers to identify strategic opportunities for developing innovative products and technologies. Furthermore, this system should be focused on successfully promoting innovation in all areas of the national economy, thereby enhancing its competitiveness in the global market.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained during this study, the following conclusions were formulated.

1. The transition to a new technological system should be based on the selection of priorities for innovative growth and scientific and technological development, the development of industrial infrastructure, and the creation of new industries. Strategic development plans should be aligned with the goals of innovative transformations, the interests of economic entities, and external and internal factors.

2. Innovative development priorities are selected based on a systemic analysis of potential across economic development areas, taking into account the existing resource base and the quality of human capital.

3. Transforming the Russian economy in line with the development of new technological standards is closely linked to the Concept for Achieving Technological Sovereignty. The use of strategic planning tools allows for the substantiation of growth priorities through a systems approach and a set of target indicators based on their sources, taking into account the existing technological and intellectual potential of the economy. On this basis, it is possible to modernize the Russian economy and reduce its dependence on imported innovative foreign technologies.

4. Accelerated growth of the country's high-tech sectors will ensure its technological sovereignty, create new jobs, increase demand for highly qualified specialists, and contribute to the growth of the population's well-being. To address these challenges, it is

advisable to use well-developed strategic planning tools.

5. The use of strategic planning tools for implementing the Concept for Achieving Technological Sovereignty of the Russian Economy is methodologically substantiated. The sequence of its practical implementation must be regulated in accordance with the national strategy for the transition to technological sovereignty at the national, regional, sectoral, and corporate levels.

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